

Study on the Seismic Behavior of Plan Irregular Buildings with Base Isolation in Seismic Zone V

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Abstract- These seismic risks are considered the prime cause for concern in seismic zones and earthquake-prone areas around the world. Over time, a sequence of earthquake motions with different seismic intensity has been used to conduct the investigation and analyze the structural dynamics. Analyses considering the effect of isolated structures showed that the isolators restrict the lateral loads transmitted to the structure, which, in turn, has the tendency to reduce the sizes of building components. In this study, design, operation, testing, and applicability of base isolation are analyzed in detail as per Indian Standards. Base isolation has been found to be one of the popular design approaches in recent times. A building structure is taken as a case study model for this study, and contemporary design tools are also applied for the analysis. Conclusions are drawn from the results obtained. We'll discuss the probable advantages of base isolation over the conventional dynamic analysis. This chapter deals with the design details of the models and step followed to design the building. This study is conducted on a G+11-story building located on soft soil. The structure is designed as a college building (with plan irregularity) situated in Seismic Zone V and analyzed using ETABS 2022. For the analysis, two models are considered: Model M-1, which has a fixed base, and Model M-2, which incorporates a base isolator. The comparative analysis between the fixed-base model (M-1) and the base-isolated model (M-2) clearly demonstrates the effectiveness of base isolation in improving seismic performance. The base-isolated structure shows reduced base shear, displacement, and overturning moments by approximately 25–30%, indicating enhanced stability and safety. Although story drift slightly increases due to controlled base movement, this behavior helps in dissipating seismic energy and reducing damage to the superstructure. Overall, base isolation significantly enhances structural resilience, minimizes earthquake-induced forces, and provides an efficient and reliable solution for earthquake-resistant design in multi-storey buildings. Overall, the comparative study clearly demonstrates that the implementation of base isolation considerably enhances the seismic performance of structures. It reduces base shear, displacement, and overturning moments while allowing controlled drift, thereby ensuring improved safety, flexibility, and durability. These outcomes confirm that base isolation is a highly effective and reliable strategy for seismic risk mitigation in multi-storey buildings.

Keywords – Base Isolation, Framed Structures, Structural Analysis, Base Shear, Bending Moment, Shear Force.

I. INTRODUCTION

Earthquakes generate severe ground motions that pose significant threats to structural safety, particularly in seismic regions. Despite continuous advancements in seismic design, construction practices, and maintenance techniques, earthquake-induced damage remains a major concern, especially for high-rise structures. Conventional seismic design methods primarily focus on collapse prevention; however, damage to non-structural components often renders buildings unusable after earthquakes, which is critical for essential facilities such as hospitals.

Numerous studies analyzing structural response under varying seismic intensities have demonstrated that base isolation

systems effectively reduce lateral forces transmitted to the superstructure. By decoupling the building from ground motion, isolators reduce seismic demand, displacement, and internal forces, allowing optimization of structural member sizes. Consequently, base isolation has emerged as one of the most effective seismic protection techniques.

In this study, the design, performance, and applicability of base isolation systems are evaluated in accordance with Indian Standards. A representative building model is analyzed using advanced numerical tools, and the seismic performance of isolated and fixed-base structures is compared. The results highlight the advantages of base isolation over conventional dynamic analysis approaches.

Recent earthquake events have provided valuable insights into structural behavior under different seismic conditions, contributing to the development of advanced mitigation strategies. Along with base isolation, innovative structural systems such as diagrids offer enhanced efficiency and architectural flexibility. Hybrid Diagrid Base Isolation Systems (HDBIS), which combine diagrid action with seismic isolation, are investigated in this study. Detailed building models are developed using ETABS software to assess seismic response parameters such as base shear, storey displacement, inter-storey drift, stress distribution, diagrid configuration, and isolator type, particularly rubber-based isolators. The findings aim to contribute to improved seismic-resistant design practices.

II. PLAN IRREGULARITY

Plan irregularity, as defined in IS 1893:2016, refers to non-uniformity or asymmetry in a building's horizontal layout due to re-entrant corners, uneven mass or stiffness distribution, diaphragm discontinuities, or non-parallel lateral load-resisting systems. Such irregularities result in non-uniform seismic response, causing torsional effects and stress concentration during earthquakes. Diaphragm discontinuities arise from large slab openings or stiffness variations, while out-of-plane offsets occur due to discontinuous vertical elements. Non-parallel systems further contribute to uneven force distribution. Plan irregularities significantly influence seismic performance, often leading to localized damage and premature failure of structural components. Eccentricity between the center of mass and center of stiffness induces torsional motion, increasing vulnerability during seismic events. Therefore, evaluation of plan irregularity is essential for accurate seismic analysis and safe structural design.

- Common features of plan irregularity include:
- Non-rectangular layouts such as L-, T-, or U-shaped plans
- Re-entrant corners
- Torsional irregularity
- Uneven distribution of mass and stiffness
- Understanding plan irregularity enables effective design of lateral load-resisting systems and compliance with seismic design provisions.

III. BASE ISOLATION SYSTEM

A base isolation system is installed between the foundation and superstructure to reduce seismic force transmission. By allowing controlled horizontal movement at the base, isolation systems significantly reduce acceleration, displacement, and structural damage during earthquakes.

IV. PRINCIPLE OF OPERATION

Base isolators increase the natural period of the structure and dissipate seismic energy, shifting the response away from the dominant earthquake frequency range.

V. TYPES OF BASE ISOLATORS

Elastomeric (Rubber) Bearings: Consist of alternating layers of rubber and steel, often incorporating a lead core for enhanced energy dissipation.

Sliding Bearings: Utilize low-friction interfaces such as Friction Pendulum Systems (FPS), suitable for large displacements and heavy structures.

Advantages

Significant reduction in seismic forces
Reduced structural and non-structural damage
Improved occupant safety and post-earthquake functionality

Limitations

Higher initial cost
Requirement of precise design and maintenance
Limited effectiveness for very soft soils and extremely tall structures

Applications

Base isolation is widely applied in hospitals, bridges, power plants, heritage structures, and high-value commercial buildings.

VI. HYBRID STRUCTURES

Hybrid structures combine two or more materials or structural systems to achieve optimal strength, stiffness, and efficiency. Common hybrid systems include steel-concrete, timber-concrete, steel-timber, and composite structures.

Benefits

High strength-to-weight ratio, Improved seismic and wind performance, Reduced construction time, Enhanced architectural flexibility

Challenges

Complex design and detailing, Higher initial construction cost, Hybrid structures are extensively used in high-rise buildings, bridges, long-span roofs, industrial structures, and sustainable construction systems.

VII. LITERATURE REVIEW

Arslan Zulifqar (2024) The optimization and improvement of Hybrid Diagrid-Base Isolation Systems (HDBIS) to increase their performance in seismically active regions is the main goal of this structural engineering project. Because of their limits in seismic resilience, typical construction methods for tall

buildings in such places offer significant hazards. It is investigated how well Smart Base Isolation systems work in diagrid and outrigger constructions. As a result, HDBIS is acknowledged as a viable option that offers strong seismic protection, cost-effectiveness, and design flexibility. A fixed-base model is contrasted with base-isolated models of diagrid and outrigger structures in order to assess the efficacy of base isolation technologies.

Tariq H.R. Bermany, S.A. Osman, Mohd Yazmil Md. Yatim (2025) Base isolation systems are one class of technologies developed to enhance the seismic performance and resilience of structures. However, these devices have a number of limitations and challenges that make their effective use for building protection against different types of seismic hazard scenarios difficult. While several base isolation techniques have been proposed in the literature to provide seismic protection to multiple structures, no detailed review has been conducted on their advantages and disadvantages and the application of Earthquake Early Warning Systems for the pre-activation of a series of isolation techniques.

This paper presents a state-of-the-art review of base isolation devices, with consideration of various advantages and disadvantages associated with base isolators under different seismic conditions. Passive, semi-active, active, and EEW-activated isolation systems are analyzed, as well as their essential parts, such as actuators, dampers, and bearings. Future research directions are suggested along with the identification of critical research gaps. According to the results, a potential remedy for the drawbacks of conventional isolation systems might be the creation of a multidirectional base isolation system that integrates EEWs for pre-activation with hybrid bearings and controllable fluid viscous dampers or piezoelectric actuators as additional damping devices. These developments can lead to more resilient, economical, and flexible base isolation techniques, especially for seismically active areas and important structures.

Abhishek Kumar, Nabal Kumar (2023) Seismic isolation is a technique that reduces earthquake-induced stresses by lengthening a structure's period of vibration. Typically, the period of the isolated structure is maintained as about two seconds. For buildings in which the fundamental period of vibration without base isolation is less than 1.0 second, isolation thus derives considerable advantages. This paper carries out an analytical study on base isolation for buildings with natural periods ranging from 1.0 to 3.0 seconds. A number of possibilities are studied to enhance the applicability of base isolation for such structures. The tactics advocated for this study are (i) stiffening the superstructure, (ii) damping the superstructure, and (iii) making the isolation system flexible. It has been observed that incorporating such provisions enhances the effectiveness of base isolation for these buildings. The objective of this study is to determine the ways in which base

isolation in structures analyzed using matching time-history and response spectrum methods can be augmented by integrating performance-based building design with the tactics outlined above. In this study, G+7 storey structures are dealt with. By increasing the structural time period—which is usually kept as two seconds for isolated structures—seismic isolation serves to reduce seismic forces. Thus, there are appreciable benefits derived for structures whose fundamental period of vibration is equal to or less than 1.0 seconds without base isolation.

Sajan K Jose, Anjali G S, Aarya S Nair, Adithya D A, Ananya Sony, Arunima A S (2021) The need for multi-story buildings has grown significantly in recent years, but these structures are more likely to sustain significant damage during earthquakes. Among passive structural vibration control systems, base isolation is thought to be one of the most useful instruments. By introducing a mechanism that enables the structure to effectively "hover" during seismic activity, this technology isolates the above-ground structure from the effects of earthquake forces. Using the Response Spectrum Method in ETABS software, a thorough analysis of 10-story RCC, steel, and composite structures with and without base isolation across multiple seismic zones is conducted in this project. The base isolation system uses lead rubber bearings that were built in accordance with UBC97. While hollow and rectangular designs work better for steel and composite structures, respectively, the plus-shaped configuration is determined to be the most appropriate for base isolation in RC structures. In contrast to steel and composite structures, it has been found that foundation isolation improves the performance of concrete structures.

VIII. OBJECTIVES

To perform comparative study of the building with base isolator and with fixed base condition.

To observe the effect of rubber isolator on the irregular building (with plan irregularity) situated on seismic zone V.

Examine and contrast structural elements such as Story displacement, Story drift, Story shear force and base shear.

IX. METHODOLOGY

This chapter deals with the design details of the models and step followed to design the building. This study is conducted on a G+11-story building located on soft soil. The structure is designed as a college building (with plan irregularity) situated in Seismic Zone V and analyzed using ETABS 2022. For the analysis, two models are considered: Model M-1, which has a fixed base, and Model M-2, which incorporates a base isolator.

M – 1 Model without base isolator.

M – 2 Model with base isolator.

Geometrical Specifications

Table 4.2 Geometrical Specifications of the Structure

Type of structure	Description
Number of stories	G+11 story
Number of Grid in X-Direction	8
Number of Grid in Y-Direction	6
Floor to floor height	3m
External walls	230 mm
Internal walls	150 mm
Total Area of the building	40m x 30m
Size of column	500 X 450mm
Size of beams	450 X 250 and 500 X 250mm
Thickness of slab	150 mm
Slab Type	Thin Shell
Floor Diaphragm	Rigid
Column Shape	Rectangular
Beam Shape	Rectangular

Figure 4.1 Plan of Story 1 to Story 5

Figure 4.2 Plan of Story 6

Figure 4.3 Plan of Story 7

Figure 4.4 Plan of Story 8

Figure 4.5 Plan of Story 9

Figure 4.6 Plan of Story 10

Figure 4.7 Plan of Story 11

Figure 4.8 Side - Elevation of building with Isolation

Figure 4.9 Front - Elevation of building with Isolation

Figure 4.10 3D building with Isolation

Figure 4.12 Side - Elevation of building without Isolation

Figure 4.11 3D building with Isolation

Figure 4.13 Front - Elevation of building with Isolation

X. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the seismic analysis of a G+11 storey college building with plan irregularity, located on soft soil in Seismic Zone V, modeled and analyzed using ETABS 2022. Two structural configurations were studied: Model M-1 (fixed-base) and Model M-2 (base-isolated). The effect of base isolation was evaluated in terms of story displacement, story drift, story shear, overturning moment, and base shear.

Story Displacement

For both models, story displacement increases progressively from the base to the top, which is typical under lateral loading. However, the fixed-base model (M-1) shows consistently higher displacement values compared to the base-isolated model (M-2) in both X and Y directions. The displacement reduction in M-2 is nearly uniform across all stories, with an average reduction of 19.4–19.9%, indicating that base isolation effectively enhances the overall lateral stiffness and reduces seismic response.

Story Drift

Story drift in both models increases from the top toward the mid-height and decreases near the base, reflecting normal seismic behavior of multi-storey buildings. The base-isolated model (M-2) exhibits higher drift values (about 100–150%) compared to M-1. This increase is expected and desirable, as the isolation system allows controlled movement at the base, dissipating seismic energy and reducing damage to the superstructure.

Story Shear

The story shear distribution along the height remains identical for both models in X and Y directions, confirming that base isolation does not alter the magnitude of applied lateral forces. However, the isolation system reduces acceleration and displacement demands by absorbing seismic energy. Higher shear values are observed in the Y-direction, indicating directional stiffness variation.

Overturning Moment

Overturning moments increase from the top toward the base, reaching maximum values at the foundation level. The base-isolated model (M-2) shows a significant reduction in overturning moments compared to M-1. In the X-direction, a reduction of approximately 26–28% is observed, while in the Y-direction the reduction is about 28–29% across all storeys. This reduction decreases foundation demand, minimizes uplift potential, and improves overall seismic stability.

Base Shear

The fixed-base model (M-1) experiences a base shear of 6510.84 kN, whereas the base-isolated model (M-2) shows a reduced base shear of 4587.61 kN, corresponding to an approximate 30% reduction. This significant decrease is

attributed to the decoupling effect of the isolators, which limit the transmission of ground motion to the superstructure.

Base Shear	
M - 1	6510.84
M - 2	4587.61

Overall Observations

The comparative study clearly demonstrates that base isolation significantly improves seismic performance by reducing story displacement, overturning moment, and base shear while allowing controlled drift. These results confirm that base isolation is an effective seismic mitigation technique for multi-storey buildings located in high seismic zones.

XI. CONCLUSION

This chapter presents a summary of the seismic analysis of a G+11 storey college building with plan irregularity, located on soft soil in Seismic Zone V, modeled and analyzed using ETABS 2022. Two analytical models were considered: Model M-1, a conventional fixed-base structure, and Model M-2, a structure incorporating a base isolation system. The study evaluates the influence of base isolation on key seismic parameters such as story displacement, story drift, story shear, overturning moment, and base shear.

The results indicate that story displacement increases from base to top in both models, which is typical under lateral loading. However, the base-isolated model (M-2) shows consistently lower displacement values, with an average reduction of about 19–20% compared to the fixed-base model (M-1). This confirms the effectiveness of base isolation in limiting lateral movement and enhancing structural stability.

The story drift pattern in both models shows an increase toward mid-height and a reduction near the base. The base-isolated model exhibits higher drift values (about 100–150%), which is expected and desirable, as it reflects controlled flexibility at the isolation level, enabling energy dissipation and reduced structural damage.

Story shear distribution remains similar in both models, indicating that base isolation does not significantly alter the applied lateral forces but modifies their transmission mechanism. Higher shear values are observed in the Y-direction, suggesting directional stiffness variation. Base isolation helps reduce acceleration and displacement responses while maintaining comparable shear profiles.

Overturning moment values increase toward the base in both cases, with maximum values at the foundation level. A reduction of approximately 26–29% in overturning moment is observed in the base-isolated model, highlighting its role in reducing foundation demand and improving seismic safety.

Base shear results further validate the benefits of isolation. The fixed-base model records a base shear of 6510.84 kN, whereas the base-isolated model shows a reduced value of 4587.61 kN, corresponding to an approximate 30% reduction.

Overall, the study demonstrates that base isolation significantly improves seismic performance by reducing base shear, displacement, and overturning moments while allowing controlled drift. These findings confirm that base isolation is an effective seismic mitigation technique for multi-storey buildings in high seismic zones.

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